

Studies in Natural and Synthetic Flavonoids. Part II. Epoxidation of Chalkones

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Synthesis of some new 2'-benzylorychalcone epoxides has been effected. Monoperphthalic acid has been found effective in the epoxidation of 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalcone (I). Reduction of 2'-benzyl-orychalcone epoxides by LiAlH_4 has been found to furnish 1,3-diarylpropane-1,2-diols in good yields.

Epoxide formation is an important stage in flavonoid synthesis. The epoxides of simple chalcones can be readily prepared either with the aid of alkaline hydrogen peroxide or peracids; their properties have been investigated by several workers¹⁻⁴. Epoxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide of chalcones having a free 2'-OH group has not been successful because under these conditions flavonols^{5,6}, dihydroflavonols^{7,8}, and their mixture or aurone⁹ formation may take place. In order to obtain chalcone epoxides for some synthetic work progressing in these laboratories, 2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalcone epoxide (II) was successfully prepared, though in poor yield, by the use of monoperphthalic acid. Its structure has been confirmed by analysis and IR spectrum which has the characteristic absorption bands in the hydroxyl (3500 cm^{-1}), carbonyl (1700 cm^{-1}), and epoxide (1260 cm^{-1}) region. Its poor yield is ascribed to the competitive Baeyer-Villiger oxidation.

Bognar and Stefanovsky¹⁰ prepared chalcone epoxides by treating chalcones with alkaline hydrogen peroxide after protecting the 2'-OH group and these were converted

1. Welts and Schaeffer, *Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 2327.
2. Black and Lutz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5990.
3. Wasserman and Aubry, *ibid.*, 1955, **77**, 590.
4. Zimmerman *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 108.
5. Algar and Flynn, *Proc., Roy. Irish Acad.*, 1934, **B42**, 1.
6. Oyamada, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1935, **10**, 182.
7. Murakami and Irie, *Proc. Imp. Acad. Tokyo*, 1935, **11**, 229.
8. Reichel and Stendel, *Annalen*, 1942, **553**, 83.
9. Geismann and Fukushima, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1686.
10. *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 143.

to dihydroflavonols in good yields on treatment with acidic reagents. According to Seshadri and co-workers¹¹, the course of the reaction depends on the substituents in the styryl part and also on the reaction conditions. Some new chalcone epoxides have been prepared under the present scheme. The 2'-OH group has been protected in these cases by benzylation and good yields of benzyl ethers and chalcone epoxides have been obtained.

(III) R=Me; R'=R''=H.

(IV) R=Me; R'=H; R''=OMe.

(V) R=Me; R'=R''=OMe.

(VI) R=H; R'=R''=OMe.

(VII) R=Me; R'=R''=H.

(VIII) R=Me; R'=H; R''=OMe.

(IX) R=Me; R'=R''=OMe.

(X) R=H; R'=R''=OMe.

In the present communication reduction of 2'-benzyloxychalcone epoxides by LiAlH_4 has been studied and the products have been shown to be 1,3-diarylpropane-1,2 diols¹² (XII & XIII).

(XI) R=H.

(VII) R=Me.

(XII) R=H

(XIII) R=Me

These propane-1,2-diols may function as the possible intermediates for the synthesis of many heterocyclic compounds. Attempts to cyclise these compounds by various reagents are in progress in these laboratories.

EXPERIMENTAL

2'-Benzyloxy-5'-methylchalcone (II).—2'-Hydroxy-5'-methylchalcone¹³ (8 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution (200 ml) with benzyl chloride (5.3 ml), sodium iodide (2 g.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (23 g.) until the ferric chloride reaction became negative. It was filtered, acetone distilled, and the residue steam distilled. The yellowish compound was crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow needles (7.8 g.), m.p. 115-16°. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 84.1; H, 6.1%).

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

11. *Tetrahedron*, 1964, 20, 1141.

12. Cf. Herz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2928.

13. Ballantine and Whalley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3224.

2-Benzoyloxy-5'-methylchalkone Epoxide (VII).—To compound (III) (2 g.), dissolved in acetone (30 ml), was added a mixture of hydrogen peroxide (20 vol., 10 ml), aqueous 8% NaOH solution (2.4 ml), and methanol (5 ml). The solution was shaken and brought to boiling occasionally during 1½ hr. and was left overnight at the room temperature. To this was added water till turbidity and the solution was kept in a refrigerator. A white crystalline compound was obtained which was crystallised from methanol in silky needles (1.6 g.), m.p. 120-21°. Its IR spectrum showed strong peaks at 1670 (C=O) and 1245 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). (Found: C, 79.4; H, 6.2. C₂₃H₂₀O₅ requires C, 80.2; H, 5.8%).

2-Benzoyloxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalkone (IV).—2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalkone¹⁴ (4 g.) was refluxed in acetone (100 ml) with benzyl chloride (3 ml), sodium iodide (2 g.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (12.5 g.); the reaction mixture was treated as described for (III). The resulting compound was crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow needles (3.9 g.), m.p. 137-38°. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 6.3. C₂₄H₂₂O₅ requires C, 80.4; H, 6.1%).

2-Benzoyloxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalkone Epoxide (VIII).—To compound (IV) (1 g.), dissolved in acetone (15 ml), a mixture of hydrogen peroxide (20 vol., 5 ml), 8% aqueous NaOH solution (1.25 ml), and methanol (2.5 ml) was added and the mixture worked up as described for (VII). The resulting compound was crystallised in colorless prisms from ethanol (0.8 g.), m.p. 102-103°. Its IR spectrum showed strong absorption peaks at 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O) and 1250 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). (Found: C, 77.1; H, 6.3. C₂₄H₂₂O₆ requires C, 77.0; H, 5.8%).

2-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalkone Epoxide (II).—Monoperphthalic acid was prepared from finely powdered phthalic anhydride (4.5 g)¹⁵ and to its ethereal solution (150 ml) was added 2'-hydroxy-5' methyl-4-methoxychalkone (1 g.); the resulting solution was slowly refluxed for 8 hr. The reddish solid obtained after complete removal of the solvent by distilling under reduced pressure was digested with dry chloroform (50 ml). The insoluble phthalic acid was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to dryness *in vacuo*, yielding a reddish semisolid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate and ethanol as a colorless solid, m.p. 150-51°. It was recrystallised from methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 152-53°. It developed a bluish green colour with ferric chloride. IR absorption bands at 3500 cm⁻¹ (-OH), 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), and 1260 cm⁻¹ (epoxide). (Found: C, 71.3; H, 5.5. C₁₇H₁₆O₆ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.6%).

2-Benzoyloxy-5'-methyl-3,4-dimethoxychalkone (V).—2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-3,4-dimethoxychalkone¹⁶ (1.5 g.) was refluxed in acetone (35 ml) with benzyl chloride (1.4 ml), sodium iodide (1 g.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4.5 g.); the mixture was worked up as described in a similar case. The compound was crystallised from ethanol in yellow flakes (1.6 g.), m.p. 108-109°. (Found: C, 76.9; H, 6.6. C₂₃H₂₄O₆ requires C, 77.3; H, 6.1%).

2-Benzoyloxy-5'-methyl-3,4-dimethoxychalkone Epoxide (IX).—Compound (V) (1 g.), dissolved in acetone (15 ml), was treated as in a similar case above. The resulting compound was crystallised from methanol in shining needles (0.85 g.), m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 6.5. C₂₃H₂₄O₇ requires C, 74.3; H, 5.9%).

14. Auwers and Anshutz, *Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 1543.

15. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1951, p. 768.

16. Marathe, *J. Univ. Poona, Sci. & Tech.*, 1958, 14, 63.

2'-*Benzoyloxy-3,4-dimethoxychalkone* (VI).—2'-Hydroxy-3, 4-dimethoxychalkone⁷ (3 g.) in acetone (80 ml) was added to a mixture of benzyl chloride (2.2 ml), sodium iodide (2 g.), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (7.5 g.); the mixture was refluxed till it showed negative ferric reaction. It was worked up in the same way as described above. The resulting compound was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles (3g.), m.p. 89-91°.

2'-*Benzoyloxy-3,4-dimethoxychalkone Epoxide* (X).—Compound (VI) (2 g.) was dissolved in acetone and worked up as described for (VII). It was crystallised in pale yellow needles, (1.7g.), m.p. 99-101°. (Found: C, 74.5; H, 6.1. $C_{24}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 73.8; H, 5.6%).

1-(2'-*Benzoyloxy*)-3-*diphenylpropane-1,2-diol* (XII).—2'-Benzoyloxychalkone epoxide¹⁰ (XI) (2 g.) was added to an ice-cooled suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (0.8 g.) in dry THF (100 ml) in small instalments; the mixture was boiled under reflux for 2 hr. On cooling, the excess reducing agent was decomposed with methyl formate (5 ml) in ether (20 ml); the solution was then acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil., 50 ml). The organic layer was separated and the residue extracted with ether (3×30 ml). The combined extracts were washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Removal of the solvent afforded a yellowish viscous liquid which was crystallised in shining plates (0.8 g.) from a 1:2 mixture of benzene and light petroleum, m.p. 80-81°. It showed negative ferric reaction. (Found: C, 78.7; H, 7.0. $C_{22}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 79.0; H, 6.5%).

Acetylation of compound (XII) in presence of pyridine and acetic anhydride afforded a colorless *acetate* which was crystallised in shining needles from ethanol, m.p. 112-113°.

1-(2'-*Benzoyloxy-5'-methyl*)-3-*diphenylpropane-1,2-diol* (XIII).—Compound (VII) (0.9g.) was added to an ice-cooled solution of $LiAlH_4$ (0.3 g.) in THF (50 ml) in small instalments. Rest of the procedure was the same as described for (XII). The resulting viscous oil was crystallised from petroleum (60-80°) in colorless needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 102-104°. It showed negative ferric reaction. (Found: C, 79.4; H, 7.0. $C_{23}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 79.3; H, 6.8%).

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